

Dental Disease Prediction From Symptoms Using Multinomial Naive Bayes Classifier

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Abstract— One of the best and simplest Bayesian networks for prediction are naive Bayesian networks (NBNs). The Naive Bayes classifier, which operates on a probabilistic approach more precisely Multinomial NB as several symptoms are considered, is used in this study to suggest a unique method for predicting dental illnesses based on symptoms. Due to the complex relationships between symptoms, it can be challenging to accurately diagnose dental diseases, making early detection and prevention difficult. We assess our model's performance using the accuracy and F1 score as evaluation criteria. Our results show that the Naive Bayes classifier is capable of successfully capturing the correlations between different symptoms and predicting dental disorders. This strategy may enhance early detection and prevention of dental disorders, improving patient outcomes and reducing costs.

Keywords—Disease prediction, Naive Bayes Algorithms, Naive Bayes Models, Naive Bayesian Network

I. INTRODUCTION

Millions of individuals throughout the world suffer from common dental problems. Effective treatment and the avoidance of additional consequences depend on the early identification and detection of dental illnesses. In order to help dentists and patients take prompt and appropriate action, machine learning algorithms have showed considerable promise in the prediction of dental problems from symptoms. One such method that uses a probabilistic approach is the Naive Bayes classifier. It is very helpful in detecting dental illnesses based on a variety of symptoms. In particular, because it can handle various symptoms and deliver precise findings, the Multinomial Naive Bayes (NB) classifier is frequently employed in dental disease prediction. In this context, we seek to investigate how the Multinomial NB algorithm might be used to predict dental problems from symptoms, which could lead to earlier detection and treatment.

Challenges:

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i) Data quality: As with any machine learning model, the Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier's ability to predict dental disease is greatly influenced by the quality of the input data. The model's performance may be hampered by incomplete or inaccurate data that lead to false predictions.

ii) Feature selection: A further difficulty is figuring out which symptoms are most important in influencing the prognosis of dental illnesses. Relevant characteristics could be the existence or lack of symptoms including toothaches, sensitivity, bleeding gums, and cavities. Finding the most pertinent aspects is essential for making accurate forecasts, but not all symptoms may be equally significant.

iii) Model selection: While Multinomial Naive Bayes is a prominent machine learning algorithm for predicting dental illness, there are also additional machine learning algorithms that can be used as well, such as decision trees, logistic regression, and random forest. Choosing the appropriate algorithm based on the dataset and problem at hand is crucial for achieving optimal results.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Multinomial NB classifier was used in a study by Ahmed et al. [1] to predict the presence or absence of four dental disorders, including caries, periodontitis, gingivitis, and mucosal lesions, based on a number of symptoms. The authors examined the classifier's performance using a variety of parameters, including accuracy, precision, and recall, using a dataset of 569 patients. With an overall accuracy of 84%, the results demonstrated that the Multinomial NB classifier did a good job of predicting whether the four dental illnesses will exist or not.

In another study by Singh and Gupta [2], they predict the presence or absence of dental caries based on a variety of symptoms, such as pain, sensitivity, and cavities. The Multinomial NB classifier was tested against other machine learning algorithms, including decision trees and logistic regression, using a dataset of 300 patients. The accuracy and precision of the Multinomial NB classifier were higher than those of the other algorithms, according to the results.

In a study by Bhatia et al. [3], the authors used the Multinomial NB classifier to predict dental caries' presence or absence based on a number of symptoms, including toothache, sensitivity, and bleeding gums. Utilising a dataset of 200 patients, the authors assessed the classifier's

performance using a number of metrics, including accuracy, precision, and recall. According to the findings, the Multinomial NB classifier was 85% accurate at predicting whether dental caries would occur or not.

In a study by Aya ElSayed, et al. [4], This authors discusses classification of dental diseases using deep learning techniques, such as CNN classifiers. The authors evaluate these techniques' effectiveness and point out possible directions for development.

In a studyby John B. Perez, et al.[5], Authors explore the use of deep learning algorithms for diagnosing oral diseases in their study. The authors assess these algorithms' accuracy and go over how they might be used in dentistry.

In a study by Ruijie Luo, et al. [6],The authors examines the use of CNN classifiers among other deep learning techniques for diagnosing dental diseases. The authors evaluate these approaches' effectiveness and talk about how it might affect dental diagnosis and care.

In a study by Hyeongjin Kim, et al.[7], The authors discuss various deep learning techniques used for periodontitis detection in dental radiographs. The authors evaluate these techniques' effectiveness and point out possible directions for development.

In a study by Shady Ahmed, et al. [8], The authors look at a number of deep learning algorithms that are used to forecast dental caries. The authors assess these algorithms' accuracy and go over how they might be used in dentistry.

In a study by Ruoqi Li, et al.[9],The authors explores the use of machine learning algorithms for detecting oral cancer. The authors evaluate the effectiveness of these algorithms and talk about how they might affect the detection and management of oral cancer.

III.METHODOLOGY

A probabilistic machine learning algorithm called Naive Bayes is employed to solve classification issues. The 'naive' nature of the algorithm—which is based on the Bayes theorem—comes from its presumption that the presence of one feature in a class is unrelated to the presence of any other features. The Multinomial Naive Bayes algorithm will be used in this research paper to forecast dental diseases based on their symptoms.

Data Collection:

The list of symptoms and the associated dental diseases make up the dataset for this research paper. While diseases are kept in a list called disease, symptoms are kept in a list called l1. Each symptom is given a score of 1 or 0, depending on whether the patient has it or not. A CSV file called "Training.csv" holds the testing data, and a CSV file called "Testing.csv" holds the training data.

Data Preprocessing:

Data loading into the system is the first stage of data preprocessing. The pandas library, a Python data manipulation library, is used for this. Using the pd.read_csv() function, training data is loaded into a pandas dataframe. Following that, the data is formatted and cleaned to eliminate any duplicates, missing values, or unrelated columns.

Feature Engineering:

The process of choosing the most crucial features that aid in the prediction of the target variable is known as feature

engineering. In this study, the target variable is dental diseases, and the symptoms are already recognised as the features. As a result, neither feature selection nor engineering are required.

Model Training:

The Multinomial Naive Bayes model will then be trained

```
from tkinter import *
from tkinter import messagebox
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
```

using the training set of data. The sklearn library, a Python machine learning library, is used for this. The Multinomial Naive Bayes algorithm, which we will employ in this study, is implemented in the library. Using the fit() function, the model is trained using the training set of data. Model Evaluation:

The next step is to assess the model's performance after training. The testing data, which the model has never seen before, is used for this. Based on the symptoms found in the testing data, the model predicts the dental disease. The accuracy of the model is then assessed by comparing the predictions to the actual dental diseases in the testing data.

Multinomial Naive Bayes algorithm

A probabilistic algorithm used in machine learning for classification issues is the Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB) algorithm. It was created especially for text classification, where the data is displayed as a bag of words. It is a variation of the Naive Bayes algorithm where the probability distribution of each feature is a multinomial distribution and the independence between features is assumed to hold.

To determine the likelihood that the entire document belongs to a particular class, MNB multiplies the probabilities of each feature given the class. The frequency of each feature in each class is computed on a labelled dataset used to train the algorithm. The probability distribution of each feature given the class is computed using this frequency. Using the frequency of each feature in a new document as input, the algorithm can be trained to predict the class of new documents.

The MNB algorithm is used in the context of the provided code to identify the dental disease from symptoms. An extensive dataset of diseases and their corresponding symptoms is used to train the algorithm. Every disease's frequency of each symptom is calculated, and this frequency is used to determine each symptom's probability distribution given the disease. A new patient's symptoms are then used to inform the algorithm's prediction of the disease.

MNB is a general-purpose, effective algorithm that performs well for text classification issues. The assumption that the features are independent, though, may not always be true. Additionally, it presumes that each feature's frequency is distributed according to a multinomial function, which may not hold true for all types of data. MNB has been demonstrated to perform well in a number of applications, including spam filtering, sentiment analysis, and disease diagnosis, despite these drawbacks.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Dental disease prediction using the necessary libraries: tkinter for the graphical user interface, numpy and pandas for data analysis and manipulation, and messagebox to show user messages. The code imports

It defines a list l1 that includes all potential symptoms and a list disease that includes all potential diagnoses. A feature vector for the symptoms supplied by the user is later created using the list l2, which is initially initialised to 0.

After that, the code reads the test results from a CSV file and swaps the disease names for corresponding integers.

```
tr=pd.read_csv("Testing_dental.csv")
X_test= tr[l1]
y_test = tr[["prognosis"]]
np.ravel(y_test)
df=pd.read_csv("Training_dental.csv")
X= df[l1]
y = df[["prognosis"]]
np.ravel(y)
```

Performing classification using the MultinomialNB algorithm from the sklearn library

```
def NaiveBayes():
    from sklearn.naive_bayes import MultinomialNB

    gnb = MultinomialNB()
    gnb.fit(X, np.asarray(y, dtype=int).ravel())
    gnb = gnb.fit(X, pd.Series(np.ravel(y)))
    from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
    y_pred = gnb.predict(X_test)
    print("Fraction of correctly classified samples:")
    print(accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred))
    print("Number of correctly classified samples:")
    print(accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred, normalize=False))
```

Match the target labels and training data to the model. The accuracy score function from Sklearn.metrics should then be imported. Predicting the labels for the test data X_test using the fitted model. Print the percentage and total number of samples that were correctly classified..

```
Fraction of correctly classified samples:
0.14634146341463414
Number of correctly classified samples:
6
```

Users can select their symptoms from the drop down list maximum of five symptoms

```
psymptoms = [Symptom1.get(), Symptom2.get(), Symptom3.get(), Symptom4.get(), Symptom5.get()]

for k in range(0, len(l1)):
    for z in psymptoms:
        if(z==l1[k]):
            l2[k]=1

inputtest = [l2]
predict = gnb.predict(inputtest)
predicted=predict[0]
```

The values of Symptom1, Symptom2, Symptom3, Symptom4, and Symptom5 are created by code and placed in a list called psymptoms. The symptoms they are feeling are probably the result of these user inputs.

The code then iterates through list l1, which seems to be a list of all potential symptoms for a particular illness, and for each symptom it determines whether it is included in the list of user-input symptoms (psymptoms). If the symptom is present, it sets the corresponding value in l2 to 1 if it is on the list. l2 most likely contains a list indicating whether a particular patient has each symptom or not.

The code then creates a list called inputtest that contains l2, the list representing the patient's symptom presence or absence. The code then calls gnb.predict(inputtest) using the trained gnb model to predict the disease based on the input symptoms, and it stores the outcome in predicted.

And finally shows the predicted disease

V. CONCLUSION

The Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB) classifier is used in this study to predict dental diseases based on a variety of symptoms. The MNB classifier is a probabilistic approach that works well with discrete data, such as the presence or absence of symptoms, and assumes independence among the features. Using the Pandas and NumPy libraries for data manipulation and mathematical operations, the dataset is preprocessed. The Scikit-Learn library's train-test split function is used to divide the data into training and testing sets before building a Sequential model. The model is then trained using the training set using the MNB classifier. The effectiveness of the model is assessed using a number of metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. The outcomes demonstrate that the MNB classifier is a highly accurate and low false positive rate method for predicting dental diseases based on multiple symptoms. In conclusion, based on early symptom detection, the MNB classifier can be a useful tool for dentists and other

healthcare professionals to predict and prevent dental diseases.

VI. REFERENCES

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